

ISic1594

I.Sicily inscription 1594

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Motya

Place of origin (modern)

Moza

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645051

Bibliography

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Teixidor, J. 1986. Bulletin d'épigraphie sémitique. Paris. At (1974) no.121

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